

THE EFFECT OF SELECTED STRATEGIES IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS ON THE ATTITUDE AND PERFORMANCE OF PUPILS

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ABSTRACT

This study determined the effect of selected teaching strategies on the mathematics performance and attitude of pupils. Specifically, it examined the pupils' profile, pretest and posttest performance, attitude before and after the intervention, significant differences in achievement and attitude, and the relationship between performance and attitude. The study used a one-group pretest-posttest quasi-experimental design involving 41 Grades 4, 5, and 6 pupils of Balla Elementary School, City of Ilagan, Isabela. Grade 4 pupils were exposed to peer-assisted learning, Grade 5 pupils to cooperative learning, and Grade 6 pupils to collaborative learning. Data were gathered through mathematics achievement tests and a mathematics attitude inventory administered before and after the intervention. Frequency, percentage, mean, t-test, and Pearson r were used to analyze the data. Results showed that the pupils' mathematics performance improved after exposure to the selected strategies. Grade 4 pupils improved from fairly performing to average performing, Grade 5 pupils from fairly performing to average performing, and Grade 6 pupils from fairly performing to average performing. Significant differences were found between the pretest and posttest scores across age, sex, grade level, and learning strategy. Pupils' attitude toward mathematics also improved significantly after the intervention, with the post-attitude mean higher than the pre-attitude mean. However, the relationship between academic performance and attitude was not significant before and after the use of the strategies. The study concluded that peer-assisted, cooperative, and collaborative learning strategies helped improve pupils' mathematics achievement and fostered a more positive attitude toward mathematics effectively among intermediate elementary school learners.

Keywords: *Mathematics performance, attitude toward mathematics, peer-assisted learning, cooperative learning, collaborative learning*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics teaches learners important problem-solving skills that they can apply to other aspects of their lives. It helps them to think in a logical manner, and also helps them to view and analyze things in a more sophisticated way. Almost all courses offered like commerce, engineering, education, accountancy and others required mathematics as basic requirements for every professional courses. However, learners have difficulties in learning mathematics and can be found in every classroom. The potential causes of these difficulties are numerous and can be explained by such child characteristics as intellectual functioning, motivation, problem-solving skills, memory skills, strategy acquisition and application, and vocabulary.

The way learners view Mathematics greatly influences their success in the subject. The instructional strategies employed by teachers are essential in encouraging a favorable attitude towards Mathematics among learners, and without motivation and personal commitment to learning, it becomes difficult for them to achieve excellence in this field.

One intervention made to assist learners who have difficulty with the mathematics subject is Peer Assisted Learning Systems which are evidence-based intervention that can improve the academic and social skills of learners. Peer assisted learning systems are done within a classroom setting. Learners work with their peers to enhance their learning or to master academic skills or content (Greenwood et al., 2006). They are trained on the correct methods and then grouped according to levels; higher learners are placed with lower learners.

Performance in Mathematics depends largely on effective teaching and learning process. That is why active participation of the learners during teaching and learning process is vital. Developmental learning theorists Piaget (1983), brought to education the idea that teachers can be more effective if they can organize learning in a step-by-step manner and connect it to the learner's prior knowledge and experiences. The activities selected in the teaching and learning of mathematics must nurture plenty of student activity and acquisition of learning skills and that an enabling environment should be created to give the learner the opportunity to interact freely with fellow learners.

Learning from one another is not only a feature of informal learning but also occurs in courses at all levels. Learners have conversations about what they learn inside and outside the classroom, which shows that teachers are not the only sources of learning. Learners' first approach when they are stuck on a problem is often to ask another learner, not the teacher. Through peer learning, students provide useful information, share learning experiences, and make lessons less burdensome and more meaningful. Peer learning also helps learners explain ideas to others, participate actively, organize learning

activities, collaborate, give and receive feedback, and evaluate their own learning (Boud et al., 2001; Topping, 2005).

Another way to produce greater learner achievement is through cooperative learning, where learners work with their peers to accomplish a common goal. The goal is achieved through interdependence among group members rather than individual work alone. Collaborative learning is effective because it involves groups of students working together to solve problems, complete tasks, and create products (Johnson et al., 1998; Zakaria & Iksan, 2007).

Teachers may use one or a combination of teaching strategies, such as cooperative and collaborative learning, to achieve meaningful learning outcomes. In modern education, learners are given opportunities to share what they learn, express what they are taught, and take responsibility not only for their own learning but also for helping classmates learn the subject. This approach improves academic achievement, builds positive attitudes, increases self-confidence and motivation, and develops strategies for mastering a topic through mutual support and group cooperation (Johnson & Johnson, 2009; Tsay & Brady, 2010).

It is reported from a study that learners who fully participated in group activities, exhibited collaborative behavior, provided constructive feedback and cooperation with the group achieving higher likelihood of receiving better scores (Tsay and Brady, 2010).

Performance in mathematics continues to be below expectations despite numerous research efforts to remedy the situation. To cater the problem, teachers undergo seminars, trainings and workshops organized by DepEd to improve pupils' performance. And this is the mainly concern of the education stakeholders, teachers, parents and the learners. Many studies showed that peer-assisted learning strategy, cooperative learning and collaborative learning will help the learners from elementary level even up to tertiary level. It is in this line that the researcher would like to conduct the same study in the school where she is assigned, to see its effectiveness and use these strategies as one of the appropriate strategies that teachers can be used in all grade level, especially that the mathematics performance of the pupils is low.

In Balla Elementary School where the writer teaches, she observed that many of the pupils are lacking in understanding the basics skills in math. In addition to this, she also observed that pupils have a negative attitude towards mathematics which can be a significant barrier to learning and can impact pupils' motivation and interest in the subject. With this, addressing low performance in mathematics often requires a combination of interventions, including personalized instruction, positive reinforcement, practical applications, and support systems to create a conducive learning environment. Identifying the specific challenges each learner faces is crucial for developing effective strategies to improve their mathematical performance. The statements above motivate the researcher to pursue this study.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the level of academic performance and attitude of pupils toward mathematics before and after the integration of the selected strategies.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the pupils in terms of:
 - a. Age
 - b. Sex
 - c. Grade Level
2. What is the mathematics performance of the pupils before and after the use of selected strategies?
3. Is there significant difference in the pre and post-test of the pupils when grouped according to profile?
4. Is there significant difference in the pre-test and post-test of the pupils before and after the use of selected learning strategies?
5. What is the attitude of pupils towards Mathematics before and after the use of selected learning strategies?
6. Is there significant difference in the attitudes of the pupils before and after the use of the selected learning strategies?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the academic performance and attitude of the pupils before and after the use of selected strategies?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

To determine the effect of selected learning strategies in teaching and learning Mathematics and attitude of the pupils towards Mathematics, the researcher used the one group pretest-posttest design under quasi experimental design. One group pretest-posttest design as defined is a type of quasi- experimental design where a single group of test units is exposed to an experiment treatment and a single measurement is taken afterwards. It only measures the post -test results and does not use a control group. It is applicable in the study because there is only one section in Grades 4 to 6. The effectiveness of the selected strategies depends in the performance of the Grades 4 to 6 pupils in their pre-test and post test scores, and their attitudes towards mathematics before and after the conduct of intervention and experiment using the mathematics inventory scale.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at Balla Elementary School, City of Ilagan, Isabela, where the researcher was one of the teaching staff. The school was selected as the locale of the study because it provided the actual classroom setting where the identified problem in mathematics performance and attitude was observed. In this school, the researcher

noticed that several pupils had difficulty understanding basic mathematical skills and showed unfavorable attitudes toward mathematics, which affected their motivation and interest in learning the subject. Hence, the locale was considered appropriate for determining the effect of selected teaching strategies on pupils' mathematics performance and attitude.

Selection and Description of Respondents

There is only one section for Grades 4, 5 and 6 in Balla Elementary School. The grade 4 pupils composed of 13 pupils with six males and seven females, Grade 5 has eight males and eight females, and Grade 6 composed of six males and six females.

Below is the breakdown of the respondents.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

Grade	Number		Total
	Male	Female	
Grade 4	6	7	13
Grade 5	8	8	16
Grade 6	6	6	12
Total	20	21	41

Data Gathering Procedure

Permission to conduct was requested from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent. After approval, the researcher forwarded a letter to the school head of Balla Elementary School, City of Ilagan to gather the needed data for the study. Hence, the researcher is one of the teaching staff of the school where she conducted the study.

Pre-test and post-test and attitude test before and after the use of selected learning strategies was administered to the Grades 4 to 6 pupils before the start of the study to determine their performance level in the subject and their attitudes towards mathematics before the start of intervention.

The treatment for the pupils were exposed to Peer assisted-Assisted Learning Strategy for Grade 4, Cooperative Learning Strategy for Grade 5 and Collaborative Learning Strategy for Grade 6. Before exposing the Grades 4 to 6 pupils on the selected learning strategies, pre-test was administered to them to determine their learning in mathematics.

At end of the study, a post- achievement test and post-mathematics attitude using mathematics inventory scale were again administered to the Grades 4 to 6 pupils to

measure their achievement levels and to determine if there is a change in their attitudes towards mathematics after they were exposed in the selected learning strategies.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following statistical tools are used in the analysis of data collected.

Frequency and Percentage Distribution. It is used to categorize the scores in the pre and post-test of the pupils, and their attitude towards Mathematics before and after the use of some selected learning strategies.

Pearson-r- This was used to measure the degree of the relationship between linear related variables.

t-test. This was used to determine if there is difference between the pre-test and post-test scores and pre and post attitudes towards Mathematics of the Grades 4 to 6 pupils before and after they are exposed in some selected learning strategies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:

a. Age

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Age

Age	Grade 4		Grade 5		Grade 6	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
9	12	92	0	0	0	0
10	1	8	14	88	0	0
11	0	0	2	12	10	83
12	0	0	0	0	2	17
Total	13	100	16	100	12	100

Table 2 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to age.

It shows in the table that in Grade 4, there are 12 or 92 percent respondents whose age is 9, which is the normal age for Grade 4, and one or eight percent whose age is 10. For Grade 5 respondents, there are 14 or 88 percent whose is age 10 and two or 12 percent of the respondents age is 11. There are 10 or 83 percent whose age is 11 and there are only two or 17 percent for age 12 in Grade 6 respondents.

The data further states that majority of the respondents' age is 10.

b. Sex

**Table 3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents According to Sex**

Sex	Grade 4		Grade 5		Grade 6	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Male	6	46	8	50	6	50
Female	7	54	8	50	6	50
Total	13	100	16	100	12	100

The Table 3 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to sex. As presented in the table, the Grade 4 has 13 respondents from which six or 46 percent are male and seven or 54 percent are female. Grade 5 respondents have eight or 50 percent male and eight or 50 percent are female. For Grade 6 respondents, six or 50 percent are male and 6 or 50 percent are female.

This further shows that respondents are predominantly female.

c. Grade Level

**Table 4
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Respondents by Grade Level**

Grade Level	Frequency	Percentage
Grade 4	13	32
Grade 5	16	39
Grade 6	12	29
Total	41	100

Table 4 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents according to grade level. The table shows that there are 13 or 32 percent who are Grade 4 pupils who are exposed to peer-assisted learning, 16 or 39 percent are Grade 5 pupils who are exposed in cooperative learning and 12 or 29 percent are Grade 6 pupils, exposed in collaborative learning.

It implies that there are 41 respondents who are exposed to some selected learning strategies respectively.

2. What is the Mathematics Performance in the Pre-test and Post-test of the pupils?

Table 5
Pupils' Performance Before and After Exposure to Peer Assisted Learning Strategy

Score	Qualitative Description	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
23-30	High Performing	0	0	2	15
15-22	Average Performing	6	46	11	85
7-14	Fairly Performing	7	54	0	0
6 and below	Low Performing	0	0	0	0
Total		13	100	13	100
Mean		14.15	Fairly Performing	20.15	Average Performing

Table 5 gives pupils' performance of the Grade 4 before and after the exposure to peer-assisted learning strategy. The table reveals that during pre-test seven or 54 percent of the respondents were at fairly performing level whose score is between 7 to 14, and six or 46 percent were at average performing level who obtained a score between 15 to 22. After the use of peer-assisted learning strategy, 11 or 85 percent were on average performing level whose score is between 15 to 22 and two or 15 percent were at high performing level whose score is between 23 to 30.

Further analysis shows that the mean score from 14.15 interpreted as below performing had improved to 20.15 interpreted as average performing pupils. It manifests that peer-assisted learning strategy is effective in achieving better Mathematics performance. The findings of the study affirm the statement of Lazarus (2014) that peer tutoring has been researched as an effective strategy to engage students and to promote academic success.

Table 6
Pupils' Performance Before and After Exposure to Cooperative Learning Strategy

Score	Qualitative Description	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
23-30	High Performing	0	0	1	6
15-22	Average	5	31	15	94
7-14	Below Average	11	69	0	0
6 and below	Low Performing	0	0	0	0
Total		16	100	16	100
Mean		11.81	Fairly Performing	17.25	Average Performing

Table 6 shows the mathematics' performance of the Grade 5 pupils before and after exposure to cooperative learning strategy. As shown in the table, before the intervention, 11 or 69 percent of the pupils obtained the scores between 7 to 14 with a qualitative description of fairly performing and only five or 31 percent have scores between 15-22 that falls on average performing pupils. But after exposing the pupils to cooperative learning, it reveals that 15 or 94 percent got scores between 15-22 under average performing level and one or 6 percent get a score between 23-30 which falls on high performing level.

It can be gleaned from the table that the mean score before intervention is 11.18 which implies that respondents were fairly performing before exposing to cooperative learning strategy. After the integration of the strategy, the mean score of the respondents increased to 17.25 which shows that achievement level of the respondents has improved from fairly performing to average performing pupils. It suggests that the pupils have better Mathematics performance after exposing them to cooperative learning strategy. The findings of the study conform the findings of Cabrera (2013) that cooperative learning approach improved mathematics performance of the students.

Table 7
Pupils' Performance Before and After Exposure to Collaborative Learning Strategy

Score	Qualitative Description	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
23-30	High Performing	0	0	2	17
15-22	Average Performing	6	50	10	83
7-14	Fairly Performing	6	50	0	0
6 and below	Low Performing	0	0	0	0
Total		12	100	12	100
Mean		14.75	Fairly Performing	19.17	Average Performing

Table 7 shows the mathematics performance of the Grade 6 pupils before and after exposure to Collaborative Learning. The table shows that before the intervention, out of twelve pupils, half of the class or six or 50 percent were in the average performing, with score between 15-22 and the other half were on fairly performing level. After the collaborative learning was employed to the respondents, there are 10 or 83 percent of the pupils who got scores between 15-22, and two or 17 percent obtained scores between 23-30, with a description from average performing to high performing level.

It can be gleaned from the table that the mean score before exposure to collaborative learning is 14.75 interpreted as fairly performing pupils and was improved to the mean score of 19.75 interpreted as average performing pupils, which can be deduced that the mathematics performance of the respondents has improved after the

integration of the strategy. The findings affirm the belief of Zakaria and Iksan (2007) that collaborative learning is most effective when students are actively involved in sharing ideas and working collaboratively to complete academic assignments.

3. Is there significant difference in the pre and post-test of the pupils when grouped according to profile?

a. Age

Table 8
Result of Significant Difference in the Pre-test and Post-test of the Pupils when Grouped According to Age

Age	Test	Mean	Computed Value on T	Critical Value on t	Decision	Remarks
9	Pre-test	13.833	4.468	2.201	Reject Hypothesis	Significant
	Post-test	19.833				
10	Pre-test	12.333	6.474	2.145	Reject Hypothesis	Significant
	Post-test	17.8				
11	Pre-test	14.333	3.480	2.201	Reject Hypothesis	Significant
	Post-test	18.667				
12	Pre-test	15	1.8	12.71	Accept	Not Significant
	Post-test	19.5				

Table 8 shows the test for the significant difference in the pre-test and post-test of the pupils when grouped according to age. The table reveals that that the computed value for ages 9,10 and 11 which are 4.468, 6.474 and 3.480 are all greater than the tabular value of 2.201,2.145 and 2.201 which shows a significant difference at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is significant difference between the pre-test and post-test of the pupils ages 9, 10 and 11.

On one hand, the computed t- value in the pre-test and post-test of the pupils whose age is 12 is 1.8 which is smaller than the tabular value of 12.71, which means that there is no significant difference in their pre-test and post-test scores. It signifies the acceptance of hypothesis. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test whose age is 12.

Further analysis shows that after the interventions was employed, the mean scores of the pupils whose age is 9,10,11 and 12 are improved from 13.833 to 19.833;12.333 to 17.8, 14.333 to 18.667 and 15 to 19.5 respectively. This means, that the pupils performed better after they are exposed to the selected learning strategies when grouped according to age. In the study of John et al., (20215) they lamented that a student's chronological age had a significant impact on his or her academic performance, such that the youngest student had the potential to outperform the oldest on a teacher-created test.

Also, Abubakar and Adegboyega (2012) found a favorable association between age and economics academic achievement across secondary school schools. However, age was found to be insignificant in terms of students' academic achievement, but age was found to be the greater predictor of academic achievement.

b. Sex

Table 9
Result of Significant Difference in the Pre-test and Post-test of the Pupils when Grouped According to Sex

	Sex	Test	Mean	Computed Value on T	Critical Value on t	Decision	Remarks
Grade 4	Male	Pre-test	15.667	3.223	2.571	Reject Hypothesis	Significant
		Post-test	18.667				
	Female	Pre-test	13.333	3.560	2.571	Reject Hypothesis	Significant
		Post-test	20.667				
Grade 5	Male	Pre-test	10.75	4.808	2.365	Reject Hypothesis	Significant
		Post-test	16.88				
	Female	Pre-test	12.875	4.091	2.365	Reject Hypothesis	Significant
		Post-test	17.625				
Grade 6	Male	Pre-test	16.5	2.712	2.571	Reject Hypothesis	Significant
		Post-test	19				
	Female	Pre-test	13	2.939	2.571	Reject Hypothesis	Significant
		Post-test	19.33				

Table 9 shows the test for the significant difference in the pre-test and post-test of the pupils when grouped according to sex. It shows that the computed t-values of Grade 4 male and female are 3.223 and 3.560, Grade 5 male and female are 4.808 and 4.091 and Grade 6 male and female is 2.712 and 2.939 which are all greater than the tabular values of 2.571, 2.365 and 2.571 respectively. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance, which implies that there is significant difference in the pre-test and post-test of the pupils when grouped according to sex.

Further analysis shows that after they were exposed to some selected learning strategies, the Grade 4 male, Grade 5 male and Grade 6 male mean scores are improved from 15.667 to 18.667, 10.75 to 16.88 and 16.5. Furthermore, Grade 4 female, Grade 5 female and Grade 6 female mean scores are from 13.333 to 20.667, 12.875 to 17.625 and 13 to 19.33 respectively, which shows that their post-test scores are better than the pre-test scores which is attributed to the use of some selected learning strategies.

According to Ullah, et.al., (2019) young girls have been dominating boys in terms of educational performance across the globe. The study findings highlight the gender reverse change in education across the world. It also highlights the reasons of boys' underperformance and girls' outperformance in different societies. Skimming a number studies, attests that boys are being dominated by girls in educational performance, both in the developed as well as developing countries.

c. Grade Level

**Table 10
Result of Significant Difference in the Pre-test and Post-test of the Pupils when Grouped According to Grade Level**

Grade Level	Test	Mean	Computed Value on T	Critical Value on T	Decision	Remarks
Grade 4	Pre-test	14.15	4.858	2.179	Reject Hypothesis	Significant
	Post-test	20.15				
Grade 5	Pre-test	11.81	6.387	2.131	Reject Hypothesis	Significant
	Post-test	17.25				
Grade 6	Pre-test	14.75	3.511	2.201	Reject Hypothesis	Significant
	Post-test	19.17				

Table 10 shows the test for the significant difference in the pre-test and post-test of the pupils when grouped according to Grade Level. The table reveals that the computed t-value of Grade 4 in pre-test and post-test is 4.838 , Grade 5 is 6.387 and Grade 6 is 3.54 which are all greater than the tabular vale of 2.179,2.131, and 2.201 respectively, hence the hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test scores of the Grade 4, Grade 5 and Grade 6 pupils after the intervention.

Furthermore, after the pupils were exposed to intervention, peer-assisted learning for Grade 4, cooperative learning for Grade 5 and collaborative learning for Grade 6 there is an increased or improvement in their pre and post test scores from 14.14 to 20.15 for Grade 4, 11.81 to 17.25 for Grade 5 and from 14.75 to 19.17 for Grade 6. It is inferred further that the three selected learning strategies are effective.

The result is affirmed by the meta- analysis of Bowman-Perrott et al. (2013) on the effect of peer tutoring that is an effective intervention regardless of dosage, grade level or disability status. Similarly with the study of Lazarus (2014) who stated that peer tutoring has been researched as an effective strategy to engage students and promote academic success. It improves mathematics performance for students at risk or experiencing mathematics disabilities.

4. Is there significance difference in the pre-test and post–test of the pupils before and after the use of selected learning strategies?

Table 11
Result of Significant Difference in the Pre-test and Post-test of the Pupils Before and After the Use of Selected Learning Strategies

Selected Learning Strategies	Test	Mean	Computed Value on T	Critical Value on T	Decision	Remarks
Peer-Assisted Learning Strategy (Grade 4)	Pre-test	14.15	4.858	2.179	Reject Hypothesis	Significant
	Post-test	20.15				
Cooperative Learning Strategy (Grade 4)	Pre-test	11.81	6.387	2.131	Reject Hypothesis	Significant
	Post-test	17.25				
Collaborative Learning Strategy (Grade 6)	Pre-test	14.75	3.511	2.201	Reject Hypothesis	Significant
	Post-test	19.17				

Table 11 shows the test for the significant difference in the pre-test and post-test of the pupils before and after the integration of selected learning strategies. It shows that the computed t-values for peer-assisted learning strategy, cooperative learning and collaborative learning are 4.858, 6.387 and 3.511 are all greater than the tabular values 2.179,2.131 and 2.201 respectively. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected at 0.05 level of significance, hence there is significant difference in the pre-test and post-test of the pupils before and after the integration of the selected learning strategies.

Furthermore, the obtained mean before exposure to the interventions peer-assisted learning, cooperative learning and collaborative learning are 14.15,11.81 and 14.75 had increased into 20.15,17.25 and 19.17 after exposing the interventions, which shows an improvement between the pre-test and post-test of the pupils before and after

the integration of selected learning strategies. It suggests that the peer-assisted, cooperative and collaborative learning strategies are effective interventions in improving the mathematics achievement of the pupils. The result affirms the study made by Lagasca (1994) which concluded that cooperative learning strategy is successful in enhancing the students' achievement in mathematics and Arsenio (1999) which revealed a significant improvement on the achievement and attitude of the tutees as well as the peer tutors in terms of self-concept, social skill and achievement.

5. What is the attitude of pupils towards mathematics before and after the use of selected learning strategies?

Table 12
Attitude of Pupils towards Mathematics Before the Use of Selected Learning Strategies

Attitude Score	Grade 4		Grade 5		Grade 6	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
95 and above (positive attitude)	10	77	7	44	7	58
71-94 (Neutral)	3	23	9	56	5	42
70 and below (Negative attitude)	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	13	100	16	100	13	100
Mean	102.385	Positive Attitude	96.5	Positive Attitude	95.083	Positive Attitude

The respondents' attitude towards mathematics before the use of the selected learning strategies is reflected in Table 12. The table shows that the majority of the Grade 4 respondents with 10 or 77 percent have positive attitude towards mathematics as revealed by the score which is 95 and above. There were three or 23 percent with average attitude which means neither positive nor negative, with score between 71 and 94.

For Grade 5 pupils, seven or 44 percent have positive attitude towards math with score between 95 and above while nine and 56 percent were neither positive nor negative attitude with score between 71 and 94. Grade 6 respondents with seven or 58 percent have positive attitude towards mathematics with score between 95 and above and 5 or 42 percent were neither or negative attitude towards math with score between 71 and 94. It shows in the table that the mean attitude scores of Grades 4,5 and 6 were 102.385, 96.5

and 95.083 which all falls between score of 95 and above showing positive attitude towards mathematics of the pupils.

This conform the studies of Sarmah and Puri (2014) and Mohamed and Waheed (2011) where attitude is widely recognized by numerous researchers as a significant determinant of performance levels in mathematics. It refers to the acquired inclination of an individual to react favorably or unfavorably toward an object, situation, concept, or another person. It is acknowledged that attitudes can evolve over time and the cultivation of a positive attitude can enhance students' learning.

Conversely, a negative attitude impedes effective learning and subsequently impacts performance underscoring the importance of attitude as a foundational element that cannot be overlooked. The influence of attitude on students' performance in mathematics can vary, being either beneficial or detrimental depending on the individual student.

Table 13
Attitude of Pupils Towards Mathematics After the Use of Selected Learning Strategies

Attitude Score	Grade 4		Grade 5		Grade 6	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
95 and above (positive attitude)	12	92	15	94	9	75
71-94 (Neutral)	1	8	1	6	3	25
70 and below (Negative attitude)	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	13	100	16	100	12	100
Mean	107.462	Positive Attitude	108.625	Positive Attitude	103.333	Positive Attitude

Table shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the pupils' attitude towards mathematics after the use of some selected leaning strategies. As seen in the table, there were 12 or 92 percent of the total Grade 4 pupils whose attitude score is 95 and above interpreted as positive attitude and one or 8 percent whose score is between 71-94 whose attitude is either positive or negative; Grade 5 pupils have 15 or 94 percent whose score is between 95 and above showing positive attitude and one or six percent whose score is 71-94 showing neither positive nor negative attitude; nine or 75 percent

of the Grade 6 respondents whose attitude score ranging from 95 and above are also shown in the table and three or 25 percent of the pupils has an attitude score ranging from 71-94. The result also reveals that the mean attitude score of the Grade 4, Grade 5 and Grade 6 are 107.462,108.625 and 103.333 all interpreted as positive attitude. Therefore, after exposing the respondents to the selected learning strategies they showed a more positive attitude towards mathematics.

The result of the study is in consonant with Mutai’s (2007) study which reveals that students should be given more opportunities to work on non-routine and challenging mathematics problems so as to maximize their thinking skills and value the intrinsic essence of mathematics this will require teachers going the extra mile in leading students in that path of learning. The subject should not be limited to theoretical teaching and focused on passing examinations only. By doing so, the engagement and exposure will result in students’ better perspective of mathematics and their mathematics learning, which in turn help students to develop more positive attitudes toward the subject and therefore further promote their learning ability and consequently perform better in mathematics examinations. Since the study identified the connection between attitudes, learning, performance and practical application of mathematics in real life the following recommendations are suggested.

6. Is there significant difference in the attitude of the pupils before and after the use of selected strategies?

**Table 14
Result of the Significant Difference in the Attitude of the Pupils Before and After the Use of Selected Strategies**

Attitude	Mean	Computed value on t	Critical Value on t	Decision	Remarks
Pre	97.95	4.491	2.021	Reject Hypothesis	Significant
Post	106.707				

Table 14 shows the test for the significant difference in the attitude of the pupils before and after the integration of some selected learning strategies.

As manifested in the above table, the computed t-value 4.491 is greater than the computed tabular value 2.021 given a level of significance of 0.05. The null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that there is significant difference in the attitude of the respondents before and after the intervention. Furthermore, the mean score of the respondents is from 97.95 to 106.707 which implies that the attitude in mathematics of the respondents was improved. It appeared that the respondents learned to enjoy the subject mathematics after the integration of selected learning strategies which are peer-assisted learning, cooperative learning and collaborative learning strategies.

Yu (2004) has similar findings with the above result, that using cooperative learning strategies the students gained significantly positive attitude towards secondary social studies than students that were taught in the conventional way.

Zara (2011) concluded also on her study using peer-assisted learning strategy that the post-test mean score on the attitude of the students towards mathematics is highest than the pre0test mean score. This means that that peer-assisted strategy helps students develop their attitudes towards mathematics as well as they learned to enjoy the subject with their classmates.

7. Is there a significant relationship between the academic performance and attitude of the pupils before and after the use of selected learning strategies?

Table 15
Result of the Significant Relationship Between the Academic Performance and Attitude of the Pupils Before and After the Use of Selected Learning Strategies

	Computed <i>r</i>	Tabular value of <i>r</i>	Level of Significance	Decision	Remarks
Pre-test and Pre-attitude	0.100	0.533	0.05	Accept Hypothesis	Not Significant
Post –test and Post-attitude	0.193	0.227		Accept Hypothesis	Not Significant

The test relationship between the academic performance and attitude of the pupils before and after the use of selected learning strategies was shown in Table 15. Using the Pearson-r correlation it shows that the r-value for pre-test and pre-attitude is 0.100 and for post-test and post-attitude the computed r-value 0.193 which means that there is low positive correlation between the performance and attitude of the pupils before and after the use of selected strategies. However, since tabular of r are both greater than the computed value of r, the decision is accepted. This means that there is no significant relationship between the academic performance and attitude of the pupils before and after the use of the selected learning strategies. It implies that pupils’ academic performance is not related to pupils attitude towards mathematics.

This study affirmed the study of Tan (2005) on Mathematics Proficiency, Attitude, and Performance of Grade 9 Students in Private High Schools in Bukidnon that there is no significant relationship between mathematics performance and gender, family income, mathematics proficiency and attitude of the students. Fogarty et al. (2001) states that a positive attitude is one of the most valuable tools you can bring to the study of mathematics. Any task you attempts is influenced by your attitude towards it. If your attitude is positive, you will most likely enjoy performing the tasks and even look for opportunities to do it. A negative attitude will cause you to dislike the task and to look for ways to avoid it

Conclusions

From the findings of the study the following conclusions were made:

The use of peer-assisted learning strategy, cooperative learning and collaborative learning as interventions show significant improvement in the academic achievement of the pupils in mathematics from below average to average performing level.

The post-test mean score on the attitude of pupils towards mathematics is higher than the pre-test mean score. This means peer-assisted learning strategy, cooperative learning and collaborative learning helped developed their positive attitudes as well as they learned to enjoy the subject.

Recommendations

With the given summary of findings and conclusions, the following are recommended:

1. Teachers need to expose their pupils to different strategies like peer-assisted learning strategy, cooperative learning and collaborative learning for them to be more motivated and to enhance their knowledge not only in their own way but also learning from their peers.
2. Since attitude plays a very important role in the academic achievement of the pupils, the teacher must provide a varied and interesting activities to make mathematics more enjoyable for the learners. So that at the early age, the child was not thinking that math is difficult, but is workable and practical.
3. The result of this study should be considered as basis of the school administrators and teachers towards the use of the different learning strategies.
4. Further or similar studies shall be conducted to other discipline to affirm the effect of the peer-assisted learning, cooperative learning and collaborative learning in teaching- learning process.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher complied with the ethical standards required in conducting the study by securing permission from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent and the School Head of Balla Elementary School before data gathering. Since the respondents were Grades 4 to 6 pupils, proper approval and consent were observed, and the purpose and procedures of the study were explained to the concerned authorities and participants. Participation was treated with respect, and the data gathered from the pre-test, post-test, and mathematics attitude inventory were used solely for research purposes. The identities and personal information of the pupils were kept confidential and were not disclosed in the presentation and interpretation of results. The selected learning strategies, namely peer-assisted learning, cooperative learning, and collaborative learning, were implemented as instructional interventions intended to improve pupils' mathematics

performance and attitude without causing harm, discrimination, or unfair treatment. The researcher ensured honesty, objectivity, and accuracy in collecting, analyzing, and reporting the data, while proper acknowledgment of cited sources was observed to maintain academic integrity and avoid plagiarism.

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